

ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL NETWORKS OF ARBITRARY STRUCTURE

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Digital signal processing systems play an important role in modern technology. They can be implemented in a number of structures. The structure of a digital system determines the number and order of execution of some elementary functions, such as arithmetic operations, storage, and others. This order is often critical to implement a signal processing algorithm with the required efficiency. Signal processing algorithms can often be implemented in a number of structures.

The selection of an appropriate digital system structure is carried out as part of the design process. Typically, a comparison of structures from an appropriate set is based on a simulation of the system. To this end, it is necessary to develop a model of the system. For more efficient development of a number of models, it is desirable to use some unified method of system description and modeling.

The described model is based on the representation of the system as a signal graph. Nodes of the graph represent internal signals while ribs represent signal transfers. There can be distinguished two types of ribs: with one cycle delays and without delays. This graph is described by the matrix equation linking current node signals to the node signals at the previous time. The signals transformations are described by a matrix of ribs without delays and a matrix of ribs with one cycle delays. The first one contains transfer coefficients of the ribs the second contains symbols z^{-1} representing one cycle delay. Input signal connection to the system is described by a column vector containing only one non-zero element corresponding to the node to which the input is connected. An additional row vector is used to identify the node from which output signal is read.

The matrix equation can be solved in time domain to obtain time domain response to a specified input signal. To allow this the matrix of ribs without delays must be transformed to calculable form. That is it must be low triangular.

In the Z domain solving the equation with respect to node signals we obtain transfer function and frequency response of the system.